

PREPRINT

Corona Fictions Anthologies. On the Compilation of Hispanophone and Francophone Corona Fictions in the First Lockdown¹

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Abstract

This article examines eight anthologies (4 francophone, 4 hispanophone) conceptualized and composed during the first lockdown in the worldwide COVID-19 crisis, so-called Corona Fictions anthologies. Against the background of the classic anthological format, it describes the reasons indicated by the different editors for their anthologization endeavors, revolving around the three groups of categories of *documentation and preservation*, *support and empowerment*, as well as *inspiration and preparation*. Hereon, the article explores predominant topics, genres, and narrative situations in the Corona Fictions anthologies, supporting these findings with examples from the collections. Finally, it discusses what lessons about the COVID-19 crisis can be taken from them extending beyond literary studies.

Key words: Corona Fictions, anthology, narratives, SARS-CoV-2, pandemic, writing

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1 Introduction

After the WHO declared the SARS-CoV-2 epidemic a worldwide pandemic crisis on March 11, 2020 (cf. Adhanom Ghebreyesus 2020), a stay-at-home policy was imposed in many countries of the world lasting on average for two months (from mid-March to mid-May 2020).³ This COVID-19 induced lockdown became “a unifying experience for billions of people across the world, [...]” in the following weeks (Collins 2021; BBC News 2020).⁴ During this new collective experience of staying “at home unless [there was the] need to go out for certain reasons, such as going to work, buying food, or taking exercise” (Collins 2022), two inclinations could be observed in the realm of cultural reception and production.

In the first place, already at the beginning of this lockdown, a rapid increase in the reception of fictional narratives relating to communicable diseases was measured: on the video-streaming platform Netflix, for example, movies, such as *Outbreak* (1995) or *Contagion* (2011) were among the most watched movies in March 2020 (cf. Clark 2020). Next to these cinematic ‘pandemic fictions’ (cf. Research Group Pandemic Fictions 2020, 322f.), a new interest emerged in existing written pandemic fictions, such as *Il Decamerone* (1349-1353) by Giovanni Boccaccio and *La peste* (1947) by Albert Camus, which were broadcasted for collective consumption on the radio and through online readings.⁵

In the second place, during this period many authors and filmmakers – professionals and non-professionals alike – began producing their own (written or audiovisual) fictional narratives, relating to the COVID-19 pandemic and drawing on everyday media and political discourse as well as on previous pandemic fictions. These cultural productions – subsumed under the term Corona Fictions (cf. Research Group Pandemic Fictions 2020, 322f.) – approach and negotiate the COVID-19 pandemic from a variety of perspectives and use different media formats and genres for this purpose. The Corona Fictions⁶ produced in the wake of the first

³ More than 100 governments (cf. Dunford et al. 2020; Ritchie et al. 2020) imposed what were referred to as lockdown measures by the end of the same month in order to interrupt infection chains and subsequently relieve healthcare systems. The measures implemented ranged from school closures and travel restrictions to the complete closure of entire sectors of the economy and also included contact restrictions and curfews for specific population groups (cf. DWDS 2022).

⁴ The term lockdown as well as its Spanish synonym ‘confinamiento’ were even elected word of the year 2020 at the end of the same year (cf. Collins 2021; BBC News 2020; FundéuRAE 2020).

⁵ For example, during the first lockdown participatory public lectures of *Il Decamerone* and *La peste* were organized on social media platforms (e.g., #Décaméron-19, #lirelapeste) as well as on the radio (e.g., Austrian radio station fm4).

⁶ The Corona Fictions within Romance-languages are collected in an OA bibliographical Corona Fictions database (cf. Hobisch et al. 2021-).

lockdown show an inclination toward short and collaborative formats and genres, such as a turn to music videos (cf. Obermayr/Hobisch 2023), to series (on the Web and on TV, cf. Mateos Pérez 2021) as well as to the publication of (prose and poetry) anthologies. These tendencies in the early audiovisual and written productions of Corona Fictions can be attributed on the one hand, to the demands of our social media-driven world, which prefers quick media⁷ formats and genres, and on the other hand, to the sense of community that is created and strengthened by working together (although mostly remotely) on a common music, film, or book project (cf. Hobisch et al. 2022, 194-198; Völkl/Obermayr 2023).

Based on these observations, this article examines the following research questions:

- (1) What purpose do anthologies fulfill in general and the Corona Fictions anthologies in particular according to their editors?
- (2) What are the common characteristics of the Corona Fictions anthologies?
- (3) What general lessons extending beyond literary studies do these anthologies and their content teach us?

In order to answer these questions and to illustrate transnational and translingual tendencies in the making of these Corona Fictions anthologies, exemplary anthological data from French- and Spanish-speaking cultural areas will be examined. Therefore, a sample of four francophone and four hispanophone anthologies uniting contributions from the global north (e.g., Canada, France, Italy, Norway, the Netherlands, Spain, the United States) as well as from the global south (e.g., Argentina, Chile, Colombia, Cuba, Mexico, Peru, Uruguay) was chosen for this study. These Corona Fictions anthologies were all designed (and some even already published) in spring 2020 during the first COVID-19 induced lockdown. In total, the eight anthologies comprise of 152 texts:⁸ 61 in French and 91 in Spanish.

After an initial introduction to the anthological format in general, the focus is placed on the self-description of the Corona Fictions anthologies by their respective editor(s); then, on the characteristics concerning topics, genres, and narrative situations of the anthological

⁷ Quick media is defined here following Friedman/Schultermandl (2016, 4) as "an umbrella term for the cheap, easily accessible, and omnipresent tools of communication which allow us to connect to each other spontaneously and effortlessly and which include both messaging platforms such as text and Skype and social media outlets such as Facebook and Twitter."

⁸ With the term 'text' I am referring here to the written material in prose, poetry, or drama which appeared in the Corona Fictions anthologies, with some of this occasionally accompanied by visual images.

content gathered through qualitative and quantitative analysis. Against the background of these results, the article finally discusses the added value of the anthological text collections emanating from the first COVID-19 induced lockdown for other disciplines.

2 Anthologies in general

Anthologies commonly regroup a collection of (written) texts or text passages by different authors, who a specific community (literary, philosophical, scientific etc.) deems to have had a considerable importance within a specific epoch, for a certain genre or on a particular topic. For example, the French author Voltaire will most likely always be included in an anthology focusing on the 18th century, Virginia Woolf and Judith Butler in a Gender Studies anthology and texts by Fanon, Said and Bhabha in an anthology on Postcolonial Studies.

The history of anthologies, however, has only been studied to a relatively moderate extent. Looking at literary dictionaries, it is not even common to discover an entry for 'anthology'. In the 2013 German-language publication *Handbuch Kanon und Wertung. Theorien, Instanzen, Geschichte* (Engl. *Handbook Canon and Assessment. Theories, Instances, History*), Stefanie Lethbridge (2013, 179-182) overcomes this deficit with a contribution on this matter. In her article, she describes anthologies as collections of texts of at least three authors on a specific topic, genre, or epoch. Their characteristic features are (a) the retrospective selection of texts from a larger text pool and (b) their subsequent composition as a collection. (c) Anthologies are cheap and usually (d) compact print products that first make texts accessible and then (e) become legitimate within institutions, such as schools and universities. Their primary and best-known purpose is thus to function as instruments of canonization and anthologies sometimes even equate with the canon. The etymological Greek origins of the term – consisting of 'anthos' (Engl. 'flower', 'blossom') and 'legein' (Engl. 'to gather', 'to collect') – indicate the distinctiveness of the literary blossoms collected within them. Every anthological collection therefore also assesses and selects its content entailing the omission of other texts.⁹ The selection criteria depend on the focus the editors intend to give the anthology. They can be of a thematic or formal-aesthetic nature, can give a historical

⁹ Only in the early 1970s, revisionist debates around literary canons emerged in the context of the canonization of literary texts, increasingly questioning the mechanisms of exclusion with regard to works by women writers and ethnic minority writers (cf. Rippl/Straub 2013). For a general understanding of why female thinkers have been marginalized and obliterated for centuries in Western patriarchal civilizations, see, for example, Lerner (1986 and 1993).

insight or overview, concentrate on a specific genre or include multiple text genres. Due to practical reasons, however, anthologies usually prefer short literary forms.

As will be seen in the following chapters, most criteria for anthologies are also valid for the Corona Fictions anthologies with one slight, but not insignificant difference.

3 Corona Fictions Anthologies

In countries implementing a stay-at-home policy in spring 2020, the collective lockdown came along with the closure of cultural sites, such as museums, theatres, or cinemas, and the cancellation (or postponement) of performances, such as concerts, exhibitions, or book tours, leaving artists of different fields without either work or an income for a considerable period of time. In the midst of this unprecedented cultural standstill, it seems only natural that artistic communities as well as creative minds sought for other modes of expression.¹⁰

In the literary realm, several dozens of topical poetry and prose anthologies were conceptualized.¹¹ Arranged under the theme of COVID-19, these collections of short texts were produced either as soft-cover publications, as pdf-books, or on websites in the year 2020 and also within weeks and months of the first lockdown. Such a rapid anthologization is indeed astonishing since the composition of an anthology usually is – as mentioned above – the work of retrospective selection and collection.

The prospective approach under the sign of the COVID-19 crisis can be explained by the almost simultaneous and worldwide lockdown and the unprecedented nature of its implementation. This new and shared collective experience instigated the editors of the Corona Fictions anthologies mentioned here to either launch their respective book projects with a public call for contributions or with a request to colleagues and fellow citizens of various backgrounds to contribute to their anthology. In fact, each editor/editorial team followed at least one of the subsequent three purposes when conceptualizing their anthology: (1) they either aimed at *documenting and preserving* this exceptional collective experience, which was perceived as a ‘historical moment’ in Western History already in March 2020 (cf. Redacción Infobae 2020); and/or (2) they wanted to *support and empower* writers and readers alike in the ways of how to cope with this unprecedented experience; and/or (3) they wanted to

¹⁰ For an overview of the impact on different art sectors during the COVID-19 pandemic, their thriving at all times of crises as well as the possible future of the arts and artists, see Daniel (2021).

¹¹ Since the bibliographical data on Corona Fictions is regularly updated, please look for the search term ‘anthology’ in the Corona Fictions Database in order to inform yourself about the latest number of anthologies (cf. Hobisch et al. 2021-).

inspire new and concrete ideas for a post-pandemic world thereby *preparing* for possible futures.

3.1 Anthological purpose

The respective anthological paratexts (cf. Genette 1997) mention the three purposes either in their epitext (e.g., in the call for contributions, on a relating website, or in an interview about the publication) or in their peritext (e.g., in the preface or already in the title, as in the case of *Imaginer l'après* (Collectif 2020), meaning ‘imagining what comes after’ the lockdown or pandemic, which were largely perceived as coinciding at that point in history). To get a deeper insight into the intended purposes, this chapter will describe the editors’ endeavors of each Corona Fictions anthology, starting with the ones aiming primarily at *documenting and preserving* the present pandemic experience (while also recalling the pre-pandemic world), followed by those wanting to *support and empower* the coping strategies of all those in lockdown, and finally those *inspiring* new visions and *preparing* for what may lie ahead.

3.1.1 Document and preserve

The anthology *Bitácora del virus. Palabras del reposo* (Engl. *Virus Logbook. Words of Rest*) was put together and published by Virginia Giacosa and Lila Siegrist in Rosario, Argentina, in mid-April 2020 already. The Spanish language anthology comprising 30 texts, arose from the idea that this collectively experienced crisis constitutes a historical moment which shall not be forgotten: “*Bitácora del virus surge de la necesidad de ponernos a pensar en este momento histórico que estamos viviendo*”¹² (Redacción Infobae 2020). In addition to writers, journalists, or poets, the Argentinian editors also invited health professionals, artists, teachers and academics to contribute to this collection. Their aim was to give room to their ideas and emotions as well as to circulate their sharp, intimate, lively, and vibrant thoughts in this ‘time of rest or quietness’ (Span. ‘reposo’), i.e. the first lockdown. Hence, this publication metaphorically designated as logbook (Span. ‘bitácora’), keeps track of the particular challenges at the beginning of the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic crisis, through which large parts of the world navigated almost simultaneously. Instead of expecting any concrete answers to the crisis management, the editors rather left room for questions such as: how the role of the

¹² “*Bitácora del virus* arises from the necessity to start thinking about this historic moment we are living” (author’s translation).

state and public policies affects the private sphere; how identity is reconfigured during this exceptional experience; or how each subject inhabiting planet Earth is concerned by this very particular threat (cf. *ibid.*).

Among the first published Corona Fictions anthologies one can also find the 23 texts of the online collection *Récits infectés* (Engl. *Infected Stories*) launched by the Montreal-based editorial team Léonore Brassard, Benjamin Gagnon Chainey, and Catherine Mavrikakis.¹³ With this collection, the editors sought to particularly preserve the 'pandemic spontaneity' as the writings were composed in barely three weeks and rendered public in early June 2020. They invited renowned authors, such as Régine Robin, Marie-Célie Agnant, or Ouannesssa Younsi, to narrate their perception of the COVID-19 pandemic and its impact on them. Their texts evoke the tragic, comic, utopian, or disastrous dimensions of the crisis not by rational thought, but rather translate its affective power on the individual and the collective. Their stories "nous font ressentir la manière dont les 'crises' agissent sur nous, elles brouillent les frontières entre les corps humains, les corps des textes et les corps sociaux"¹⁴ (Brassard et al. 2020, n.p.; cf. Sarrazin 2020).

Confines: antología en tiempo de riesgo (Engl. *Limits: Anthology in Times of Risk*) was published in Argentina in August 2020 by Carlos Aprea and Roberto Pasquali and comprises 28 poems written by renowned authors. The focus on poetry is justified in the preface by emphasizing on the notion that language shapes our reality and that things only begin to exist through the act of naming them. Subsequently, poetry is considered an extraordinary form of expression since it condenses language to an infinite point in order to name things as precisely as possible (cf. Aprea/Pasquali 2020, 8-9). While the publication of newly written and unpublished texts is a common denominator for all Corona Fictions anthologies, this one stands out against the others mentioned in this article inasmuch as all contributors stem from the so-called 'risk group' of senior citizens. Additionally, Aprea and Pasquali paid attention to include contributions by authors not only originating from Argentina, but also from other countries, including Italy, Spain, Uruguay, France, the Netherlands, Peru, and Cuba. They chose these selection criteria in order to represent the pandemic crisis from their specific perspectives:

¹³ This anthology was published online (<https://recitsinfectes.com/>) shortly after the end of the first Canadian lockdown. It initially comprised 24 texts, of which the poem by Marie-Pier Daveluy was removed some time after the initial publication, but can still be found with the help of the 'Wayback machine' in the internet archive.

¹⁴ "[Theirs stories] make us feel the way 'crises' act on us, they blur the boundaries between human bodies, the bodies of texts and social bodies" (author's translation).

La consigna, fue que poemas y textos fueran escritos recientes, que las y los convocados estén muy cerca o dentro de esa franja etaria denominada ahora "población de riesgo". La pretensión, reunir, dentro de los límites temporales y vinculares posibles, voces de distintas geografías y experiencias.¹⁵ (Aprea/Pasquali 2020, 9)

3.1.2 Support and empower

The anthology *Delirios de cuarentena. Ficciones de 20 autores en la pandemia del 2020* (Engl. *Deliria of Quarantine. Fictions of 20 Authors in the 2020 Pandemic*) was published in May 2020 by the Spanish editor Carolina Corvillo regrouping 23 texts. In her preface, she also explains the intentions behind the collection: on the one hand, reflecting the aims of Aprea/Pasquali (2020) above, the short fictional stories shared the intention of helping to name (Span. 'nombrar') the overwhelming strangeness accompanying this time of collective lockdown; on the other hand, they also sought to help tame (Span. 'domar') this experience: "Breves historias para nombrar y domar lo extraño, lo que nos sobrecoge, desde la ficción y el entretenimiento"¹⁶ (Corvillo 2020, 7). Moreover, Corvillo understands the act of storytelling as a cathartic process, thereby pointing to the second aim identified. For her denominating the things around us and also the feelings within us, is an effective way to recognize ourselves as helpless in the face of destiny, but also and at the same time for taking control of our own personal destinies (cf. *ibid.* 3).

This *supporting and empowering* function is also clearly stated in the anthology *La vida en tiempos del Coronavirus* (Engl. *Life in Times of Covid-19*), which originated in a writing contest launched by Guadalupe Avalos and the Norwegian publishing house Nordlys Publicaciones, where it was also published. As explained in the preface, the contest was started because many people use writing as a means of calming themselves, of creating, healing, or ordering their thoughts: "El periodo del confinamiento hace que muchas personas usen el medio escrito para desahogarse, para crear, para sanar, para poner los pensamientos en orden, [...]"¹⁷ (Avalos 2020, 11). In response to the call, the jury received 163 texts, of which

¹⁵ "The request was that poems and texts should be written recently, that those invited should be very close to or within that age group now called 'at-risk population'. The aim was to gather, within the limits of time and networks, voices from different geographies and experiences" (author's translation).

¹⁶ "Short stories to name and tame the strange, that which overwhelms us, from the point of view of fiction and entertainment" (author's translation).

¹⁷ "The period of confinement makes many people use the written medium to unburden oneself, to create, to heal, to put one's thoughts in order, [...]" (author's translation).

10 by writers from Spain, Mexico, Italy, Columbia, the United States, France, and Norway were included in the collection which was released in August 2020 (ibid., 11-13).

3.1.3 Inspire and prepare

Although overlapping somewhat with the previous aims, the last three anthologies rather fall into the third category of *inspiration and preparation* as their stories engage with future and/or futuristic versions of the world. Such a future-oriented perspective can already be deduced from the subtitle of the French-Canadian collection *Résidence. Imaginer l'après* (Engl. *Home. Imagining What Comes After*). Their seven texts originated in the context of a “residence à domicile” (Collectif 2020, 3) – a ‘residence at home’ during the first lockdown in spring 2020 and were published by a collective editorial. The idea behind their anthological endeavor was to engage in an exercise of projection (cf. ibid., 45). The instruction for the text creation was thus to produce texts in prose or poetry inspired by the idea of that which comes *after* (Fr. ‘après’) the lockdown or the pandemic.¹⁸

Similarly to *Imaginer l'après*, the future-oriented idea for the anthology *Les femmes écrivent le monde de demain* (Engl. *Women Writing the World of Tomorrow*) emerged directly from the lockdown experience. During the first lockdown, the Collectif Sororistas – a group of 150 women from France and other francophone countries – perceived a rapid disappearance of women from the public sphere: “Très vite les femmes ont semblé s’effacer des écrans et des unes des journaux qui parlaient du monde de demain”¹⁹ (Collectif Sororistas 2020, 4). With this in mind they launched a competition aimed at collecting narratives drawing an essentially feminist vision of the future as indicated by the collection title. The instruction for the contributors was to project themselves 10 years into the future, to December 31, 2030, and to imagine in a ‘free narrative’ (Fr. ‘récit libre’) how both the personal and the collective aspects will have developed since the lockdown of 2020. Among the 589 submissions, the jury chose 20 texts for the anthology, which came out in December 2020.²⁰ These stories “parlent de nos colères et de nos désirs, de la nature bafouée, de la mort qui menace, des enfants que

¹⁸ The texts are furthermore accompanied by videos and sound works which can be consulted on the editors’ homepage: <https://www.prisedeparole.ca/residence-de-creation-imaginer-lapres/>.

¹⁹ “Very quickly, women seemed to disappear from the screens and the front pages of newspapers that talked about the world of tomorrow” (author’s translation).

²⁰ The winning stories can also be heard as spoken word podcasts on the Sororistas homepage: <https://www.sororistas.fr/concours-2020/le-podcast-2020/>.

l’on oublie, des combats que nous menons, ici et là, pour un autre monde, un monde d’égalité, de création, un monde moins bureaucratique et plus audacieux” (ibid., 6).²¹

The last anthology mentioned here is a Canadian government report under the title *La COVID-19 et la santé et le bien-être des Autochtones: nos histoires sont notre atout et témoignent de notre résilience* (Richmond et al. 2020a).²² This was published in December 2020 and consists of 10 autobiographical stories written by “Indigenous scholars, practitioners and learners” (ead et al. 2020b, 6). Although a government report, it can be listed among the Corona Fictions anthologies in the light of the fact that all of its autobiographies are structured teleologically from an already existing endpoint and therefore narrate (parts of) a life with a specific purpose (cf. Brockmeier 2001). The story-based approach, which according to the editors can be understood as “a means of humanizing COVID-19 to the broader research and policy community” (ibid., 6, 46), facilitates insights into how the COVID-19 crisis has impacted the health and wellbeing of Indigenous communities. Due to their relational and holistic understanding of life, the stories included are regrouped around the theme of relationships – with the self, the family and the community, and further to this with the land, with balance, and with self-determination. Indisputably, this anthology represents a combination of all three mentioned anthological purposes. First, it documents existing inequities in Indigenous communities, which have been magnified by COVID-19, while at the same time illustrating the possibilities of personal and community resilience. Second, because “there is little community-specific or nation-based epidemiologic data available to Indigenous leaders to inform their community responses to the pandemic” (ibid., 10), it shows how “Indigenous self-determination, leadership and place-based knowledge have successfully protected Indigenous communities in Canada during the COVID-19 pandemic” (ibid., 7). Third, the report aims at extending “Indigenous data sovereignty” (ibid., 45) to not only better support community members in the future, but also to share their insights on the resilience of the Indigenous peoples beyond their community borders.

²¹ “[T]hey speak of our anger and our desires, of the scorned nature, of the death that threatens, of the children that we forget, of the fights that we lead, here and there, for another world, a world of equality, of creation, a world less bureaucratic and more audacious” (author’s translation).

²² As an official government report published by the Royal Canadian Society, the whole collection is also available in English under the title *COVID-19 and Indigenous Health and Wellness: Our Strength is in Our Stories* (Richmond et al. 2020b).

3.2 Anthological characteristics

A quantitative survey (cf. Jannidis 2010) of the Corona Fictions anthologies was carried out to provide an overview of the characteristics the collections show. A close reading of all 152 anthological texts was the essential start for this survey. In the course of this text-oriented approach, a spreadsheet list with author-specific and text-specific information was created and filled out for each anthology. The former gathered information on the name and country of origin of the authors. The text-centered categories, which were generated through classical narratological text analysis on the basis of Gérard Genette (1980), collected thematic, formal and linguistic information of each text: i.e., text title, narrative situation, general literary genre (epic, drama, poetry) and subgenre (e.g., blog, dialogue, utopia); main subject and other subjects, spatial-temporal setting and structure as well as information on the writing style and specific stylistic devices (especially in lyrical texts). Other categories asked for explicit references to the Covid-19 pandemic and for the function of the virus in each text (e.g., expository, historiographical, moral, dramatic function, cf. Grimm 1965).²³

After this initial process, the data in the spreadsheet was revised and rectified where necessary (e.g., due to typographical errors, language mixture). The data of the closed-ended categories concerning 'explicit reference to the pandemic', 'general literary genre', and 'narrative situation' was statistically evaluated with a frequency analysis for this article, and then cross-evaluated and cross-interpreted with the entries of the open-ended categories. For a better overview, the following three subchapters examine consecutively topics, genres, and narrative situations. At the same time, however, their strong interconnectedness must also be emphasized, which will become apparent in the course of their analysis.

3.2.1 Topics

The first question that arises when examining Corona Fictions anthologies, is whether all of their texts really do reference the COVID-19 pandemic. As can be seen in figure 1, among the 152 anthological texts studied, 30 % (46 texts) do not explicitly allude to the pandemic outbreak in spring 2020, whereas 70 % (106 texts) mention the COVID-19 pandemic explicitly evoking terms such as 'coronavirus', 'pandemic', 'COVID-19', or 'lockdown'.

²³ While only a few categories, such as 'narrative situation', 'general literary genre', or 'explicit reference to the pandemic', permitted closed-ended answers from a given list of answer options (i.e., heterodiegetic/homodiegetic, epic/drama/poetry, yes/no), most other categories required or allowed open-ended answers.

Fig. 1: Explicit reference to the Covid-19 pandemic in the Corona Fictions anthologies (author's graphic).

Relating to the texts without overt pandemic references, a look at the subject categories reveals that they are concerned with reflections on personal feelings (e.g., loneliness, fears), the concepts of time and space, as well as social and ecological values regarding the notion of freedom or living in harmony with nature. While some of these texts may point the reader with their topical choice to the COVID-19 pandemic, their inclusion in a Corona Fictions anthology brings this specific connection into the still foreground, with the result that it will also be clear in the future under which circumstances all the anthological texts were produced.

Further insights into the prevalent topics tackled in the Corona Fictions anthologies were gained by a word frequency analysis of the inner-anthological text titles, since the content of a text is often announced by its title, or at least stands in some relation to it. This analysis was carried out independently for the 61 French and the 89²⁴ Spanish titles and supports the large and explicit treatment of the pandemic within the anthologies. The most frequent title words²⁵ are visualized in the respective tag clouds (fig. 2). The frequency and thus importance of each tag (i.e. title word) is represented by the font size – the larger the font, the more frequent its occurrence.

²⁴ Two of the hispanophone anthologies texts remain untitled.

²⁵ In both languages, recurrent words have been eliminated through a stopword list (Span.: a, de, del, el, en, la, los, o, que, un, una, y; Fr.: 19, à, d', dans, de, des, du, elle, en, et, il, l', la, le, les, ou, pour, sur, un, une, y).

Fig. 2: Tag clouds of Francophone and Hispanophone title evaluation (Voyant Tool 2022, cf. Flüh 2018).

Next to the expectable explicit terms concerning the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic, such as covid, virus, and pandemic (Fr. ‘pandémie’, Span. ‘pandemia’), there are those terms referring to the salient topic of life (Span. ‘vida’) during (Fr. ‘pendant’) the period (Fr. ‘période’) or time (Span. ‘tiempo’) of the COVID-19 induced lockdown (Span. ‘cuarentena’). Although the English term lockdown usually translates with ‘confinamiento’ into Spanish, the term ‘cuarentena’ – initially referring to a preventive 40 days quarantine – has been widely used synonymously in Latin American countries to designate the lockdown situation (cf. Pineda 2021). One can also distinguish terms referring to specific groups (Fr. ‘communauté’) concerned by the stay-at-home policy, such as women (Fr. ‘femmes’, Span. ‘mujer’) or Indigenous peoples (Fr. ‘autochtones’). Additionally, from the word cloud of the anthological text titles, a preoccupation with certain subjects can be deduced, such as death (Span. ‘muerte’), hospital(ization) (Span. ‘hospital’), or the feelings of being caged (Span. ‘jaula’) or ashamed (Fr. ‘honte’).

What is also noticeable in the word clouds is that the anthological corpus introduces some topics, which in pandemic fictions as well as in COVID-19 related media and political discourse, remained rather marginal, if not unheard. The highlighted words of ‘autochtones’, ‘femmes’, and ‘mujer’ point at the inclusion of topics and at the same time of voices by

women²⁶ and ethnic minorities. Indeed, whole Corona Fictions anthologies are dedicated explicitly to them. As we have seen above, in *La COVID-19 et la santé et le bien-être des Autochtones* (Richmond et al. 2020a/b), the autobiographical stories were written by Indigenous researchers (from PhD candidates to professors) from universities across Canada, relating their personal and collective experiences in their respective communities during the first months of the pandemic. Further, *Les femmes écrivent le monde de demain* (Collectif Sororistas 2020) was composed by women writers only, who imagine in their stories what will have happened in France and the world by the end of 2030. Most of their texts also stage female characters of different age cohorts and of different social milieus. Stories like “La nouvelle” (Engl. *The New-she*) (Galland 2020) and “Le printemps des femmes” (Engl. *The Women Spring* in reference to the Arab Spring in the early 2010s) (Girsch 2020) depict the biographies of two ordinary French women, who have become the first female state presidents by 2030. In “L’altermondialisme des femmes insomniaques” (Engl. *The Alterglobalism of Sleepless Women*) (Gury 2020), a female scientist and professor of sociology explains the key sociological events ten years after the COVID-19 outbreak; and in “Eldorado à quatre chiffres” (Engl. *Four-digit Eldorado*) (Wenker 2020) a Muslim migrant recounts her trajectory from her country of origin to a Greek refugee camp, where she has been stuck since the pandemic outbreak and which represents the opposite of the Eldorado she had hoped for all along.

3.2.2 Genres

The topics of the anthological texts are woven into one of the three main literary genres of prose, poetry, and drama. As can be detected from the diagrams (fig. 3), the majority of the French and Spanish texts pertain to the literary genre of the narrative; between a third and a fifth to the lyric and only a few percent to the dramatic genre. The divergent observation that more than one third of the Spanish texts fall into the category of poetry can be attributed to the fact that with *Confines: antología en tiempo de riesgo* (Aprea/Pasquali 2020) there is a poetry collection among the four hispanophone anthologies studied.

²⁶ In Corona Fictions, women appear as narrators and protagonists alike, whereas in previous pandemic fictions, women seem to be more passive minor characters or excluded at all (cf. Hobisch et al. 2022, 204).

Fig. 3: Literary genres in the Francophone and Hispanophone Corona Fictions anthologies (author's graphics).

Literary scholars commonly also group texts into subgenres. These subgenres in the Corona Fictions anthologies range from anecdote, blog, dialogue/interview, diary, dystopia and utopia to email, interior monologue, speech, reflection, account or short story from everyday life to slam poetry and rap. Among this wide range of subgenres, some (sub)genres even overlap, e.g. blog diary and narrative poetry. Notwithstanding, the most common subgenre (approx. 40 %) constitutes the everyday story, depicting all possible kinds of topics enmeshed with daily (lockdown) life from the stance of a great variety of voices. Recalling the previous subchapter, we have seen that whole anthologies give room to, for example, female and Indigenous views onto the pre-pandemic, the pandemic, and the post-pandemic world. Other topics addressed and voices heard are those pertaining to elderly people and children as well as intersectional²⁷ perspectives; even animals get a word in edgeways.

As was noted in the chapter evoking each anthology's self-description, *Confines: antología en tiempo de riesgo* (Aprea/Pasquali 2020) reunites the poems composed by female and male authors above the age of 60 belonging to the so-called 'risk group'. Some of their contributions distinctly adopt the perspective of an older narrative voice or retired narrator,

²⁷ The concept of 'intersectionality' goes back to Kimberlé Crenshaw and "promotes an understanding of human beings as shaped by the interaction of different social locations (e.g., 'race'/ethnicity, Indigeneity, gender, class, sexuality, geography, age, disability/ability, migration status, religion). These interactions occur within a context of connected systems and structures of power (e.g., laws, policies, state governments and other political and economic unions, religious institutions, media). Through such processes, interdependent forms of privilege and oppression shaped by colonialism, imperialism, racism, homophobia, ableism and patriarchy are created" (Hankivsky 2014, 2).

as in the case of "Pulmón" (Engl. *Lung*) by Gustavo Wojciechowski (2020). The stanzas of this narrative poem follow the diary form and are segmented by date indications. Between April 28 and May 1, 2020, an elderly I relates his short check-up-stay in the hospital of Buenos Aires because of respiratory problems. Other anthology texts with senior voices include, for example, Régine Robin's (2020) autobiographical reflection on how the French lockdown measures (e.g., introduction of forms to leave the house), the rhetoric used by French politicians and media (e.g., war rhetoric, infantilization of citizens, and censorship) as well as people's reactions to them (e.g., panic buying or a climate of denunciation) reminded her of her Jewish childhood in Paris of World War II. These experiences during the first lockdown of 2020 triggered Robin's wartime trauma described in her account and are announced already in its self-explanatory title: "La réactivation d'un traumatisme de guerre: Paris confiné" (Engl. *Reactivation of a Wartime Trauma: Paris Confined*). In the short story "El daño de la pena" (Engl. *The Damage of Sorrow*) by Nicanor García Ordiz (2020), the focus lies on the perspective of an old miner from the Spanish coal mining region of León, who, delirious from coronavirus disease, 'relives' his past, evoking pain, poverty, and starvation as well as alcoholism as a means of drowning his sorrows and regrets.

Children's voices are put in the foreground, for example, in "Le syndrome de noix de coco" (Engl. *The Coconut Syndrome*) (Husetowski 2020), where prevalent gender stereotypes disrupted by an adverse drug reaction of all COVID-19 vaccinated men are humorously deconstructed from a child's perspective. Another example is the short story "La visite" (Engl. *The Visit*) (Bender 2020), which takes up the everyday pandemic life from the point of view of a little girl. During the lockdown, she dreams of seeing and hugging her grand-parents again, only to find out on the day of their reunion that they have become so afraid of touch that the little girl stays "immobile et indécise. La distance qui reste à parcourir – qui nous reste tous à parcourir – soudainement redevenue si grande"²⁸ (ibid., 23).

Finally, the inclusion of anthropomorphic animal voices has to be mentioned: In "La rumba del encierro" (Engl. *Rumba of the Lockdown*) by Arlen Buchara (2020), for example, Rumba the cat stands in for her owner, who had been intended to write about the lockdown, which is circumscribed in the title with the Spanish word for prison (Span. 'encierro'). Like the rest of the world, the cat owner and author, would appear to have been overwhelmed by the

²⁸ "[She remains] still and undecided. The distance that remains to be covered – that remains for all of us to be covered – has suddenly become so great again" (author's translation).

confinement and has reached the end of her nerve. As Rumba notes in her narration of the daily occurrences:

Hace días que da vueltas por la casa, camina por las paredes, fuma al sol, anota ideas en un Word o en papelitos, lee noticias, escucha podcasts, siente angustia, alegría, culpa, llora por nada, se ríe a carcajadas por chistes pavísimos. Hace días que se sienta en la computadora frente a la ventana a intentar escribir este texto²⁹ (ibid., 51).

In stark contrast to the title of the story – ‘rumba’ which is a word also meaning ‘celebration’ or ‘party’ in Latin America – the lockdown experience, especially the lack of human closeness and warmth, is everything other than a joyful interlude. In this context and not without reason, the story ends with a sensual dream of the cat owner, in which she is again hugging and kissing other people without being afraid.

3.2.3 Narrative situation

The category of narrative situation asks for the narrating instance and distinguishes between a heterodiegetic and a homodiegetic narrator. The former being located outside of the narrated world, and the latter within it. The analysis revealed that approximately a quarter of all the texts manifest a heterodiegetic narrator whereas three quarters manifest a homodiegetic narrator (fig. 4).

The large number of homodiegetic narrations in Corona Fictions anthologies is not surprising, since they are composed of many lyrical texts³⁰ mostly rendered in the form of narrative poems together with many autofictional texts rendered, e.g., as diaries, interior monologues, or everyday stories, in which the homodiegetic narrator and the main protagonist are identical (i.e., autodiegetic narrator).

²⁹ “For days she has been walking around the house, walking on the walls, smoking in the sun, writing down ideas in Word or on paper, reading news, listening to podcasts, feeling anxiety, joy, guilt, crying over nothing, laughing out loud at the most stupid jokes. For days now, she has been sitting at the computer in front of the window trying to write this text” (author’s translation).

³⁰ The slightly higher percentage of homodiegetic narration in the Spanish anthologies can also be attributed to the greater number of lyrical texts which usually manifest the conventional literary figure of the ‘lyrical I’ or lyrical subject.

Fig. 4: Narrative situations in Francophone and Hispanophone Corona Fictions anthologies (author's graphics).

Most of the texts that have so far been mentioned are related by homodiegetic narrators from a first-person perspective. There are, however, four francophone texts, in which the homodiegetic narrator blends into the perspective of a collective 'we'. The two poems from *Imaginer l'après* (Collectif 2020), "nous fraireons cash" by Éric Charlebois (2020) and "le corona-vers" (Engl. *Covid-Verse/Covid-Worm*) by Véronique Sylvain (2020) envision how 'we as a people' will be living in the post-pandemic world. Sylvain, for example, plays with the double sense of the French term 'vers' meaning 'verse' as well as 'worm', thereby referring to the probing concerns presented in column-like (or rather worm-like) verses about the if and how of a continued existence of humanity, as human beings seem to melt more and more with technology. Also, the poem entitled "Alliées" (Engl. *Female Allies*) by Lola Cros (2020) takes on a collective female perspective underlining the importance of female networks against patriarchal structures and positions in the struggle for an egalitarian future. The fourth text "Quand il y aura moins" (Engl. *When There Will be Less*) by Clara Dupuis-Morency (2020) appropriates the perspective of a pair of siblings. In a simple and repetitive style, the children evoke the new hygienic rules during the lockdown and how they are disappointed by the promises of the adults repeating: "Quand il y aura moins de virus, nous pourrons toucher, nous pourrons saisir les choses du dehors"³¹ (ibid.). Instead of waiting for 'less virus', they start to act on their own initiative and literally escape this new strict world with the help of a friend.

³¹ "When there will be less virus, we will be able to touch again, we will be able to grasp things from outside again" (author's translation).

As we have seen in the preceding chapters, the texts in the Corona Fictions anthologies are told from a great variety of narrators, situated on the spectra between young/old, female/male, indigenous/foreign, rich/poor, center/margin, or human/animal.

Another narrator present in Corona Fictions and who remains to be mentioned, is the homodiegetic narrator in disguise of the virus or the pandemic. The 'viral' or 'pandemic autodiegetic narrator appears in "Les années aquarelle" (Engl. *Watercolor Years*) by Loredana Cabassu (2020) and "Yo soy pandemia" (Engl. *I am a Pandemic*) by Tomás Quintín Palma (2020). In "Les années aquarelle", an anthropomorphic coronavirus addresses a speech to the public in the course of its noble prize award ceremony in the year 2030. This speech includes a retrospective on how the pandemic outbreak transformed the world for the better. It describes how, like a drop on a watercolor painting, the virus changed people's awareness concerning inequalities of gender (as well as 'race'/ethnicity and class) and led to a new kind of cooperation, making the world a better and more egalitarian place for all to live in. In "Yo soy pandemia", the coronavirus thematizes its loneliness in the course of the lockdown and how it plans on leaving the quarantine in order to 'meet' other people. The short narration ends with a slightly altered replica of the famous 1970s ballad "Soy rebelde" (Engl. *I am a Rebel*), a melancholic song about a solitary person searching for happiness, friendship, and love. Instead of 'rebelde', though, one reads 'Pandemia': "Yo soy Pandemia porque el mundo me ha hecho así / porque nadie me ha tratado con amor / porque nadie me ha querido nunca oír"³² (Quintín Palma 2020, 28).

4 Anthological Lessons

As powerful world-making and self-making methods, narratives process knowledge about all areas of life and hold performative powers giving form, structure, and meaning to the contingent events of our lives (cf. Nünning A./Nünning V. 2010, 12). In short: "We tell stories to live" (Atay 2022, 202) and one can add 'to feel', as

[n]arratives are [also] particularly conducive to affective worldmaking. Their use of plot development and character perspectives invites readers into the emotional storyworlds of

³² "I am Pandemia because the world has made me this way / because no one has ever treated me with love / because no one has ever wanted to hear me" (author's translation).

novels, short stories, auto/biographical pieces, narrative poetry, newspaper articles, myths, and narrative films. (Schultermandl et al. 2022, 28)

Accordingly, the narrative texts within the Corona Fictions anthologies also represent more than just literary compositions. They assimilate explicitly as well as implicitly the COVID-19 pandemic from manifold perspectives and in diverse (sub)genres, yielding insights into the COVID-19 crisis on psychological, sociocultural, and historical levels. Building on the intentions mentioned by the anthological editors as well as on earlier work from the Corona Fictions project (cf. Obermayr/Völkl 2022a/b; Völkl 2023, Völkl/Obermayr 2023), this section provides an overview of the added value of the Corona Fictions on these levels. For this purpose, it proves instrumental to consider their functions as 'products of narration or narrative acts' (Ger. 'Erzählung') and as 'acts of narration' (Ger. 'das Erzählen') separately.

As demonstrated in Obermayr/Völkl (2022b), written and audiovisual Corona Fictions (as products of narrative acts) reflect the results of psychological and sociological studies conducted in the wake of the first lockdown. These studies consistently emphasize that restricting the vital human need of physical contact through distancing policies led to a sharp elevation of levels of anxiety, depression, loneliness, and stress on the one hand; and to a decline of mental health, resilience, and social cohesion on the other.

The Corona Fictions anthologies presented mainly depict life during the first lockdown from a personal perspective stressing the many ills and few joys of this time. The abundant choice for a homodiegetic or autodiegetic narrator is all the more significant bearing in mind the origin context of the anthologies. Originating within and with reference to the pandemic crisis, the texts staging a 'narrating I' or a 'narrating we', [...] "place[] the subject in the center and, moreover, allow[] the reader a direct insight into the emotional and mental world of the protagonists" (Obermayr/Völkl 2022a, 138). The fact that many narratives are (at least allegedly) reported from personal experience out of the COVID-19 pandemic, guarantees an assumed authenticity of their content. Representing varying degrees of 'pandemic life' including the depiction of a panoply of emotional responses to it (e.g., Žižek's (2020, 49-52) five pandemic phases of denial, anger, bargaining, depression, and acceptance, cf. Obermayr/Völkl 2022a), the anthological texts render a humanized perspective (cf. Richmond et al. 2020b, 6) of this unprecedented crisis. What is more, they facilitate an intersectional comprehension of the emotional responses through the depiction of experiences of individuals and communities marginalized on multiple levels. This, that can be subsumed as a

“testimonial [...] function” (Obermayr/Völkl 2002b, ch. 3.2) of the anthological texts, mostly aims at *documenting and preserving* the manifold experiences of the initial pandemic phase in spring 2020.

Nurturing the vital human need for contact, Corona Fictions as well as all other kinds of “stories can function as companions”, as Ahmet Atay argues (2022, 202). In his essay he explores his personal use of narratives in pre-pandemic times, in particular of mediated narratives in times of less technological progress and of reduced human contact (mainly during holiday and summer seasons spent abroad). By this means, Atay realizes that in those isolated and lonely times he “depended on books, films, and television to survive” (ibid., 203). He also deduces that this behavioral pattern of turning to stories prepared him well for the lockdown in spring 2020 as narratives “provide continuity and connection, but [...] are also a way to escape, to feel less isolated and lonely” (ibid., 204). Atay also points out that television series or soap operas can serve as a support to mark the days and keep them apart during the monotony of the lockdown agenda. Moreover, the patterns, fashions, songs, or stories of old movies, may give comfort and consistency. This functioning of “mediated narratives [and narratives in general] as companions, friends, lifelines, and ways to experience the world” (ibid., 201), amounts to the anthological editors’ endeavors to *support and empower* their audience with their collections. In the collected texts, the audience can recognize themselves and become aware of other destinies at the same time. Since Corona Fictions anthologies were published in many parts of the world (and also in other languages than French and Spanish), they, moreover, allow transnational and transcultural insights into individual and collective well-being and coping mechanisms during the first lockdown. Perceiving alternative ways of dealing with the pandemic lockdown may thus not only function as *support and empowerment*, but also as an *inspiration* for individual and collective coping strategies. This means, that next to the ‘testimonial function’, Corona Fictions – still conceived as products of narration – adopt a “therapeutic function” (Obermayr/Völkl 2002b, ch. 3.2) when entailing positive effects on those who consume them.

The ‘therapeutic function’ also operates on a second level: Shifting to the perspective of Corona Fictions as acts of narration, actively contributing to the anthologies may have also served the contributors as a coping strategy. In other words, as “a way to [either] escape” (Atay 2022, 201) or to better manage the crisis situation, as is, for example, underlined in the preface of *La vida en tiempos del Coronavirus* (cf. Avalos 2020, 11). This positive effect of the

narration on the human psyche has been confirmed by psychological research as a therapeutic tool to activate resilience (cf. Obermayr/Völkl 2022a, 131). But not just the act of narration itself, also the (virtual) coming together for a joint book project seems helpful in times of social and physical distancing. In fact, as noted in Obermayr/Völkl (2022b), in order to thrive as human beings individually and collectively, we need both physical and social contact. Writing a text for an anthology, similarly to collectively writing a novel or producing TV and web series, draws attention to solidarity – to sticking together in times of crisis, to standing up for each other and supporting each other, as most of the world’s governments are urging their citizens to do in the wake of the pandemic crisis.

Since Corona Fictions anthologies are contemporary cultural products, one can also argue that they also bear a future-oriented ‘testimonial function’ or ‘commemorative function’, since some of the anthologies purposely followed the aim of *documenting and preserving* the present. What this means is that at some point in the future they may become historically relevant as ‘memory containers’ (Assmann A. 2006, 114). With them future generations may gain, for example, knowledge about the varying hygienic practices, norms, and values in the course of the COVID-19 pandemic and our individual affective reactions to them as well as about ensuing shifts in the social fabric. Or as the US-American, Berlin-based novelist, essayist, and artist Andrea Scrima (2020) describes in the “Introduction” of her Corona Fictions anthology *Writing the Virus*:

It’s our belief that these pieces of writing, composed in unusual times and under considerable pressure, will endure as documents of a particular period of history, testimonies to states of mind we will quite possibly have forgotten as we turn our attention to the new challenges facing us. (Scrima 2020, Introduction)

The Corona Fictions anthologies not only take up individual and collective testimonies of this present age, but also prepare the cultural memory of the future. Hence, the Corona Fictions anthologies will constitute an important cultural heritage from which future generations may learn about our perceptions, fears, and hopes of today in conjunction with the COVID-19 pandemic crisis. Which of the anthological texts or contributors, however, will enter the literary canon is a question that only the future can tell and will depend largely on their content as well as their future interpretation, because “[e]in kanonischer Text [...] verkörpert die normativen und formativen Werte einer Gemeinschaft, die ‘Wahrheit’. Diese Texte wollen

beherzigt, befolgt und in die gelebte Wirklichkeit umgesetzt werden. Dafür bedarf es [...] der Deutung”³³ (Assmann J. 2005, 94-95).

5 Conclusion

The narration and compilation of texts in the wake of the COVID-19 outbreak in spring 2020 was not a surprising phenomenon, considering that human beings use narratives to make sense of themselves, the events around them, and the world at large. In this respect, the Corona Fictions anthologies analyzed in this paper demonstrate how the early mitigation measures – especially the lockdown – influenced cultural production processes, sociocultural practices, as well as individual and collective well-being. While intended as means of *documentation and preservation, support and empowerment, and/or inspiration and preparation*, the anthologies also succeed in presenting the plurality of the pandemic effects in a multi-layered and comprehensive way. Their mostly short, episodic, and fragmentary texts illustrate the extent and aftermaths of the pandemic mitigation measures in different areas of the world and on different parts of society. By introducing a diverse and partially intersectional range of voices which remained largely underrepresented in dominant pandemic discourses, the Corona Fictions anthologies render visible living conditions, experiences and hopes of children, mothers, migrants, or senior citizens at the beginning of the pandemic crisis. Thereby, these anthological texts also serve contemporary and future understandings of the COVID-19 crisis on psychological, sociocultural, and historical levels.

This study – which is by no means exhaustive, as many more Corona Fictions anthologies have been published in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic – gives a first insight into the transnational and translingual endeavors of anthologization of Corona Fictions on which future studies can build.

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³³ “[A] canonical text [...] embodies the normative and formative values of a community, the ‘truth’. These texts want to be heeded, followed, and translated into lived reality. For this it requires [...] the interpretation” (author’s translation).

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